

BM-5102

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BM5102 ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOUR

Lecturer: Pg. Dr Siti Rozaidah Pg. Hj Idris

Reflective Critique Report

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Introduction

Learning about people's behaviour have always been my interest since an early age. Observing how people interact with one another whilst managing to work individually or as a group to solve problems is something I enjoy. Management entails the process of coordinating and supervising work activities so that it is done efficiently and effectively (Schermerhorn, 2013). It is said to have four main functions, which are planning, leading, organising, and controlling. Thus, the need to understand organisational behaviour also takes place under management. Judge and Robbins (2013) stated that comprehending human behaviour plays a role in determining the effectiveness and efficiency of the organisation. The purpose of this paper is to reflect on my journey in both masters and the module. The paper would be divided into two sections to encapsulate my reflections and would be divided into my journey before, and during the first semester, undertaking BM-5102: Organisational Behaviour module.

Before

According to Judge and Robbins (2013), the basic principle of motivation is the action of an individual's intensity, direction, and persistence towards a certain goal. In this sense, motivation is explained by the amount of effort which an individual puts in and channelling said effort for a certain duration of time. I have applied Vroom's Expectancy Theory of Motivation for pursuing masters. The main reason I wanted to pursue further education is because studying is something I find exciting and it is something of comfort to me. After obtaining a bachelor's degree, majority of people would move on to pursue their respective paths, whether it is to start a career, further their studies, or other endeavours. I was certain that I would like to continue my studies regardless the institution, faculty, or major I would be in after completing my undergraduate studies. Many have encouraged me to look for a job however it was unsuccessful considering that the unemployment rate is high (Siti Fatimahwati Pehin Dato Musa and Dk Siti Rozaidah Pg. Hj Idris, 2020).

I have decided to send an application for Masters in Management offered by Universiti Brunei Darussalam School of Business and Economics (UBDSBE). This line of study is completely foreign to me; therefore, it is outside of my comfort zone. As my background of Geography and Development majorly looks at how and why people move from one place to another brings about the idea of studying how individuals work within an organisation. This has sparked a new curiosity within myself in which I want to study. In addition to this, I believe pursuing a master's in management would allow me to organise and coordinate various situations in the future. With having family members who majority have obtained a business and economics study background, I thought it would be beneficial to follow-suit.

Organisational behaviour is one of the core modules offered for this programme. Organisational Behaviour module looks at how individuals work in the organisation and how it affects the organisation. Judge and Robbins (2013) stated that organisational behaviour studies the effectiveness of an organisation based on three perspectives: individuals, groups, and organisations. It is interesting to learn the behaviours and how to overcome any challenges that arises in an organisation. With the resources, skills, and knowledge passed on from being in this programme and module, I believe that I can achieve the results that is expected. As a

result, I also believe that a reward will follow suit, by means of acquiring certification which therefore leads to my personal satisfaction as I improved to get a higher qualification.

During

In this section of the paper, I would be describing the events that has occurred throughout the semester and the workload that was given for this module. The lectures were conducted through online platforms due to the current pandemic which was something that I needed to adapt to. The module had a total of three tasks allocated to each student: a group case study, an individual analysis report, and a reflective essay. However, only two former tasks would be mentioned.

The first task was a group assignment where I had the opportunity to work with three groupmates. The title of our study was ‘Halal Education, Training, and Development: Issues and Challenges’. The paper aimed to explore the issues and challenges found in varying industries with regards to Halal education, training and development. The study had broadened my understanding of the halal processes that occurs in the south-east Asian region. During the research, we had the opportunity to attend an online symposium between Japan and Brunei Darussalam which consisted of a few universities from each country respectively. Through this research also, I have discovered how fast the Halal industry is advancing all over the globe. However, my groupmates and I could not complete our research due to several drawbacks which resulted in a change in method of obtaining data of our paper. We had opted for systematic literature review where the data articles were tabulated and categorised according to the year of publications, the country of publications, and research methods. This process was lengthy which was difficult to do due to the time constraint. Gratefully, my team and I were able to divide the work and decrease the reviewing time. Thankfully, we were able to work without disagreements.

The second task was an individual report which I titled “How Motivation Affects Across Generation Y and Generation Z in the Workplace”. As previous scholars have established that motivation of work across generations differ from one another, I decided to investigate the difference between the two recent generations and their work motivation. The paper aimed to investigate whether generation Y (millennials) and generation Z (Zoomers) had contrasting views with regards to motivation and which factors would affect them the most. I decided to use semi-structured interviews to obtain data focusing on individuals working under small and medium enterprises. However, the paper also had to be restructured so I opted to also use a systematic literature review. Due to the time constraint and lack of planning, I could not gather enough evidence for both generations to conclude the findings. Additionally, there was lack of publications that discusses generation Z as these individuals are only starting to join the workforce.

Conclusion

The first semester had taught me that different people have varying ways of completing and managing their tasks. This could bring about a harmonious or conflict into the work. Organisational behaviour module had shown how managers deal with the problems that arise, the factors that aid in managing, and how to overcome managerial concerns within the

company. I have incorporated these theories into my group assignments across the programmes however, some were not as effective. I hope to be better in allocating my time and dividing my work as this has greatly affected my schedule and assignments. I would also like to be able to gain confidence to work more independently as I still need constant feedback from lecturers and course mates to ensure that my work is in the right track. Additionally, online learning is still foreign to me which took a toll on my studies because I had difficulty in adapting. I hope that the future classes in the following semesters would take place in a more physical context that allows face-to-face interactions.

Upon reflecting on myself and the module, I have uncovered both my strengths and weaknesses when working individually or as a team. I believe that by going through the journey of pursuing master's in management would help me grow and enhance my skills. In conclusion, I have enjoyed learning this module, but I believe more could be done in providing an effective learning environment.

Reference list:

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